

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WOMEN WHO HAVE BECOME VICTIMS OF VIOLENCE

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Abstract. *The assessment of women's rights from a human rights perspective on a global scale is the result of positive changes in global progressive thinking. Naturally, the existence of women's movements on a global scale and the fact that their activities are recognized by governments indicates that the current political and governmental systems are modernizing and democratizing their structure and that the state of liberalization in the assessment of women's issues is widely developing.*

Keywords: *institute of family, harassment, stress, physical violence, emotional stress, sexual violence, economic violence, aggression.*

Introduction

The global evaluation of women's rights from the perspective of human rights is a result of the positive changes occurring in progressive global thought. Naturally, the existence of women's movements, the recognition of their activities by governments, and the ongoing modernization and democratization of political and state systems indicate the increasing liberalization in assessing women's issues. Therefore, we can assert that the 21st century will be marked by the development and progress of gender freedoms.

From this perspective, women emerge as the reserve wealth, power, creators, and builders of the new Uzbekistan in today's political and social space. Consequently, addressing their needs, expanding their opportunities, resolving their problems, and ensuring their socialization are among the state's priority tasks.

Methodology. Among foreign studies, several scholars have dedicated their research to understanding internet addiction, including K. Young, M. Griffiths, A. Goldberg, R. Davis, J. Grohol, D. Greenfield, K. Surratt, J. Morahan-Martin, P. Schumacher, and C. Chu. These researchers have defined the concept of "internet addiction," clarified assessment criteria, and developed measurement tools. Their scientific studies have contributed to the development of preventive measures by practitioners. Their work defines the current state of the issue and outlines perspectives for further research.

Today, free internet access is expanding significantly, making life easier and saving a lot of time. With the help of computers, we can find any information, communicate, shop without leaving our homes, transfer money, and complete millions of other urgent tasks— all with just the movement of a computer mouse.

At all stages of life, socialization can be interpreted as the process of an individual's development and self-transformation. This occurs through the internalization and multiplication of culture, based on a subject-to-subject approach, and influenced by purposefully created living conditions. The essence of socialization lies in the combination of adaptation and isolation of an individual within a given societal framework.

Results and Analysis

To study the socio-psychological characteristics of domestic violence, we conducted a research study. The study involved 70 women who had experienced violence (as the experimental group) and 90 women who had not (as the control group) from Tashkent and Bukhara regions. Additionally, we empirically analyzed women living with their parents, those living independently, women in their first marriages, and women in their second marriages. Initially, we present the IPS (Index of Psychological Safety) results to determine the socio-psychological characteristics of women who have been victims of violence.

Figure 1. Age Distribution of Women Who Have Experienced Violence

In our study, we selected a sample group of women who had experienced violence. The highest percentage of affected women in Tashkent city fell within the 20-30 age range, comprising 21.6% of the cases. This age group corresponds to the stage of marriage and family life. Observations indicate that jealousy is the primary motive behind violence during this period. The prevalence of violence in Tashkent is attributed to the increasing flow of information, the widespread exposure to content promoting violence, and the transformation of family values in young households.

In contrast, in Bukhara region, 14.4% of women aged 20-30 reported experiencing violence, which is lower compared to Tashkent. This difference can be linked to the presence of multi-generational families in rural areas, where parents, grandparents, and newlyweds often live together. Such family structures may contribute to a lower incidence of violence against women.

According to our research findings, the majority of women who have experienced violence in both Tashkent and Bukhara fall within the 30-40 age group, with 25.7% in Tashkent and 20.6% in Bukhara. The primary motives for violence against women in this age group are family conflicts and financial difficulties. Additionally, the main challenges for women in this period are the unequal distribution of household responsibilities and a lack of mutual respect in interpersonal relationships.

As women age, the incidence of violence decreases. Specifically, among women aged 40-50, the rate of reported violence is 3.8% in Tashkent and 8.3% in Bukhara. Among those aged 50-60, the rate is 2.8% in both Tashkent and Bukhara. This trend suggests that as individuals grow older, they develop a stronger inclination toward cooperation in interpersonal relationships.

Based on social and psychological survey data, the specific characteristics of women who have been victims of sexual and physical violence were analyzed and are illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 2. Attitudes of Women Who Have Experienced Violence Towards Themselves and Others

Among the respondents who were victims of sexual violence, 58% exhibited negative self-perception, while 22% of those who experienced physical violence showed similar tendencies. This condition is characterized by emotional rejection of oneself, lack of self-respect, devaluation of one's personality, and, most concerning, the belief that they are unworthy of a better life.

Additionally, 12% of sexual violence victims and 18% of physical violence victims developed a negative attitude toward their children. To some extent, they perceive their children as objects onto which they can project their negative emotions.

Furthermore, 64% of sexual violence victims and 74% of physical violence victims demonstrated a negative attitude toward those around them. This manifests as increased aggression, hostility, resentment toward others, destructive communication, a tendency to engage in conflicts, and an inability to regulate their emotions. They often display hostility and aggression toward everyone in their surroundings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, women who have experienced violence exhibit distinct psychological characteristics, and analyzing these traits can help strengthen rehabilitation and prevention efforts. The psychological analysis of family and marital relationships suggests that addressing emotional strain in familial interactions is a crucial social-psychological issue for every household. Additionally, previous studies have conducted extensive psychological assessments on the emotional and individual psychological conditions of such women, focusing on psychocorrectional approaches to improve their well-being.

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